

Stepwise Stability Constants and Thermodynamic Functions of Zn(II) and Cd(II) Complexes with 2-Hydroxy-5-Chloroacetophenoneanil

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The complexes of Zn(II) and Cd(II) with 2-Hydroxy-5-chloroacetophenoneanil (HCAA) have been investigated by the potentiometric titration technique in 60% v/v dioxane-water media at $\mu=0.1M$ ($NaClO_4$). The proton-ligand stability constant and the stepwise formation constants of the complexes have been determined by the Calvin-Bjerrum *pH* titration technique as used by Irving and Rossotti¹. The log *K* values have been determined by different methods. The overall changes in ΔG , ΔH and ΔS at 25°, 30° and 35° have also been evaluated.

THE complexes of Zn(II) and Cd(II) with (HCAA) have been studied potentiometrically^{2,3}. The present investigation deals with the potentiometric studies on complexes of Zn(II) and Cd(II) with 2-hydroxy-5-chloroacetophenoneanil(HCAA). The composition, stability and thermodynamic parameters like ΔG , ΔH and ΔS in 60% v/v dioxane-water media at $\mu=0.1M$ at 25°, 30° and 35° have been determined.

Experimental

The expanded scale *pH* meter of systronic with a wide range (0.01 *pH*) glass electrode and a calomel reference electrode were used for *pH* measurements.

The potentiometric titration was carried out in dioxane-water 60% v/v media at constant ionic strength ($\mu=0.1M$) maintained by adding requisite amount of sodium perchlorate solutions. The titration was carried out in an inert atmosphere. The metal perchlorate solutions were standardised complexometrically. The dioxane was purified by the method given in Vogel⁴. Carbonate free sodium hydroxide solution was prepared by a standard technique⁵. All chemicals used were of BDH AnalaR grade.

The following solutions were titrated potentiometrically against standard carbonate free sodium hydroxide (0.5 *M*) keeping the total volume of 40 ml. The temperature was maintained by immersing the cell in an electrically maintained thermostat having accuracy of $\pm 0.2^\circ$.

(I) 0.8 ml (1.062*M*) $HClO_4$ +4.0 ml (1*M*) $NaClO_4$ +11.2 ml water+24.0 ml dioxane. (II) 0.8 ml (1.062*M*) $HClO_4$ +4.0 ml (1*M*) $NaClO_4$ +112 ml water+2.0 ml (0.1*M*) ligand+22.0 ml dioxane. (III) 0.8 ml (1.062*M*) $HClO_4$ +4.0 ml

(1.0*M*) $NaClO_4$ +10.8 ml water+2.0 ml (0.1*M*) ligand+0.4 ml (0.1*M*) metal+22.0 ml dioxane.

The average number of protons associated with HCAA (\bar{n}_A), average number of ligands attached per metal ion (\bar{n}) and free ligand exponent (*pL*) were calculated using the formulas of Irving and Rossotti¹ and the formation constants were determined by the usual computational methods as given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF Zn(II) AND Cd(II) CHELATES OF 2-HYDROXY-5-CHLOROACETOPHENONEANIL AT $\mu=0.1M$ IN 60% v/v DIOXANE-WATER MEDIA

Chelate	Temp. °C	Computational methods used		
		A	B	C
Zn(HCAA) ₂	25	8.09	8.10	8.12
		5.58	5.63	5.64
		13.67	13.73	13.76
Zn(HCAA) ₂	30	7.95	7.96	8.00
		5.44	5.34	5.32
		13.39	13.30	13.32
Zn(HCAA) ₂	35	7.78	7.80	7.80
		5.32	5.18	5.20
		13.10	12.98	13.00
Cd(HCAA) ₂	25	7.95	7.96	7.91
		5.51	5.50	5.55
		13.46	13.46	13.46
Cd(HCAA) ₂	30	7.81	7.83	7.85
		5.32	5.30	5.31
		13.13	13.13	13.16
Cd(HCAA) ₂	35	7.64	7.63	7.67
		5.30	5.28	5.29
		12.94	12.91	12.94

A=Least-square method ; B=Linear Plot method ;
C=Bjerrum spreading factor method.

Results and Discussion

In the ligand it is the phenolic -OH group which takes part in the complex formation and so

the number of dissociable protons attached per ligand molecule is equal to one.

In the initial stage of the titration the ligand curve shifted to the left (or above), the acid curve due to the basic property of the tertiary nitrogen ($-C=N-$) which accepts a proton from the strongly acid medium.

The formation curve of the ligand extends over a range ($0.4 < \bar{n}_A < 1.9$) indicates the formation of the species HL and H_2L i. e., phenolic hydrogen and protonated nitrogen are completely dissociable. $\log PK_1H$ and $\log PK_2H$ belongs to the formation of HL and H_2L species respectively.

The pH meter reading B for hydrolysis of Zn(II) and Cd(II) were around 6.4 and 7.6 respectively. The deviation of metal ligand complex titration curves were noticed around pH meter reading 5.2 for Zn^{2+} and 6.0 for Cd^{2+} showing the complexation of metal ion with the ligand. The values of \bar{n} obtained were more than 1.0 suggesting 1 : 2 complexation.

Thermodynamic Parameters :

The values of the changes in free energy (ΔG) enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) accompanying the metal ligand complex forming relations have been calculated at 25°, 30° and 35° using the relations.

$$\Delta G = -RT \ln K$$

$$\frac{d \log K}{d(1/T)} = \frac{H}{4.57} \quad (\text{Equation of an isobaric}$$

reaction)⁶

$$\Delta S = \frac{\Delta H - \Delta G}{T}$$

they are summarised in Table 2.

It is concluded that with the change in temperature there was no appreciable change in the value of stability constants or which almost remain constant.

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF Zn(II) AND Cd(II) CHELATES OF 2-HYDROXY-5-CHLOROACETOPHENONANIL

$\mu = 0.1M$, Solvent : Dioxane water, 60% (v/v)			
$\Delta H = -21.92 \quad \Delta S = -10.67$			
$Zn(HCAA)_2$, K.cal/mole $Zn(HCAA)_2$, e.u.			
$\Delta H = -21.61 \quad \Delta S = -11.02$			
$Cd(HCAA)_2$, K.cal/mole $Cd(HCAA)_2$, e.u.			
Chelate	Temp. °C	*log β	- ΔG K cal/mole
$Zn(HCAA)_2$	25	13.67	18.64
$Zn(HCAA)_2$	30	13.39	18.57
$Zn(HCAA)_2$	35	13.11	18.48
$Cd(HCAA)_2$	25	13.46	18.36
$Cd(HCAA)_2$	30	13.13	18.21
$Cd(HCAA)_2$	35	12.94	18.24

* Obtained from Least-square method.

The stability constant of Zn(II) complex is higher than that of Cd(II) complex.

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